

Clock and Non-Clock Based Measurements in Quantum Mechanics

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Momentum $p=mv$ (nonrelativistic) or the relativistic form, for a particle with rest mass, may be measured in two ways, one involving a clock through the measurement of velocity and the other not, through the measurement of impulse. We suggest in this note that this dichotomy is important to the formation of quantum mechanics, at least the $\exp(ipx)$ free particle wavefunction part.

In particular, we consider one dimensional reflection-refraction of a particle with rest mass (not light) because this problem seems to give rise to both clock and non-clock based measurements. To create a scheme which accounts for both, it seems that one must use the "square root of probability". This same scheme is linked to a probability which conserves momentum.

Clock and Non-Clock Based Measurements

It is interesting that momentum may be measured with and without a clock. The clock based measurement involves measuring velocity assuming rest mass is known and the non-clock based measurement involves impulse hits. This is for a particle with rest mass. In the case of a photon, no clock is used, only impulse (or 2 slit interference etc, another approach which does not need a clock).

We suggest that this notion of clock and non-clock based measurements arises in one dimensional reflection-refraction of a particle with rest mass. In particular, we suggest that:

$$\text{Probability to reflect} + \text{Probability to refract} = 1 \quad ((1))$$

is a clock based statement because one needs to separate the process into two time periods, one in which the incident particle exists and the other in which the reflected or refracted particle exists. Furthermore, one must make repeated measurements in time in order to create ((1)).

For a single particle with rest mass m_0 in a nonrelativistic picture, one has:

$$p_1 = m_0 v_1 \text{ for } x < 0 \text{ and } p_2 = m_0 v_2 \text{ for } x > 0 \text{ with } E = \text{total energy being the same for all } x \quad ((3))$$

A physical observable which requires a clock for measurement is flux = number or probability times velocity ((4))

Thus, we suggest that ((1)) is linked with a flux type equation, nonrelativistically i.e.

$$A p_1 = B p_1 + C p_2 \quad ((5))$$

Here AA p_1 is incident flux, BB p_1 reflected and CC p_2 refracted. P_1 is proportional to v which is needed for a flux.

The main point we wish to make is that AA , BB , CC should also represent a measurable quantity like probability or number/quantity because this is needed in a flux equation. AA , BB and CC do not need a clock for measurement, at least in the nonrelativistic case.

As a result, we suggest that it is not really correct to say that ((5)) represents an equation with two unknowns B, C if $A = 1$ because the physical quantities AA, BB, CC exist and should be related without involving v , although $AA \neq BB + CC$.

The idea is that there is motivation for having two equations, one is ((5)) which requires a clock and another should not require a clock.

This idea seems to suggest that one must break up AA, BB, CC into A, B, C , but the physical quantities involve AA, BB, CC and so one may ask: What physical reason is there for this? One should not simply use a math procedure, we argue. We suggest that for AA, BB, CC one may split these into A, B, C using the concept of conservation of momentum as discussed in previous notes. Basically, AA means $A \exp(-ip_1 x) A \exp(ip_1 x)$ such that $A \exp(-ip_1 x) A \exp(ip_2 x)$ is orthogonal over x for $p_1 \neq p_2$. In other words, conservation of momentum comes at the price of existing over a length interval, but this is not an issue because $\exp(ip_1 x)$ implies that a particle with w momentum has a spatial resolution of \hbar/p . (Here \hbar is thought of as a constant.)

In such a case, it is possible to create an equation which does not involve time measurement and one that might, i.e.

$$A \exp(ip_1 x) + B \exp(-ip_1 x) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((6a))$$

$$\text{and } p_1 A \exp(ip_1 x) - p_1 B \exp(-ip_1 x) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((6b))$$

Both ((6a)) and ((6b)) may be thought of as either requiring or not requiring a clock depending on how p is measured, i.e. through a v measurement or an impulse hit.

Given that p contains an explicit v , one may combine ((6a)) and ((6b)) through multiplication to obtain: $AA p_1 - BB p_1 = CC p_2$ which may be considered as a clock based equation if one measures v in p .

There is still the notion of AA, BB, CC which do not require a clock, but represent physical quantities. These should be linked to a conservation of momentum type equation. Even though ((6a)) is: $A+B = C$ which is a conservation of square roots of AA, BB, CC , we suggest that the real physical meaning is present in taking the complex conjugate of each side of ((6a)) evaluated for any x , i.e.

$$x < 0 \quad AA + BB + 4 \cos((p_1 + p_2)x) \quad \text{and } x > 0 \quad CC$$

$\cos((p_1 - p_2)x)$ integrates to 0 as $\exp(ip_1x)$ and $\exp(-ip_1x)$ are orthogonal functions. This shows that on the LHS one has $AA+BB$, probabilities which exist for $x < 0$ in a time averaged picture and CC on the RHS.

Thus, even though $A+B=C$ is the equation ((6a)), it is linked with the ideas of $AA+BB$ and CC and momentum conservation.

As a result, we suggest that the real reason for having two equations using linear A, B, C or square root values of AA, BB, CC is to create the notion of both clock based and non-clock based measurements which both exist.

One might argue that one may multiply ((6b)) by its complex conjugate, but this simply leads to:

$$p_1 p_1 AA + p_1 p_1 BB \text{ for } x < 0 \text{ and } p_2 p_2 CC \text{ for } x > 0 \text{ when integrated over } x \text{ ((7))}$$

In this case, both relativistically and nonrelativistically, pp is linked with kinetic energy so $ppAA$ is like kinetic energy multiplied by AA a non-clock based spatial probability. This, we argue, does not really lead to any new ideas.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that clock and non-clock based measurement appearing in the same physical problem lead to an unusual creation of two equations using the square root of a non-clock based probability. For example, for one dimensional reflection-refraction of a particle with rest mass, a basic $1 = \text{probability to reflect} + \text{probability to refract}$ seems to require a clock because one needs to separate time into periods, before and after there is a potential change. We suggest that this means associating these probabilities with fluxes which are of the form $AAp_1, -BBp_1$ and CCp_2 .

In such a case, however, AA, BB, CC must have physical meaning as a quantity or probability because this is associated with the notion of flux. Thus, it is misleading to say that one only has: $AAp_1 = BBp_1 + CCp_2$ ((8)). There is also the notion of AA, BB, CC without any v , i.e. without any clock based measurements. There should be an equation involving AA, BB and CCs as well as ((8)). It seems difficult to obtain such an equation unless one uses the square root quantity values A, B, C , but there must be a physical motivation for this. We suggest that it is conservation of momentum. We argued that $AA = A\exp(-ipx)A\exp(ipx)$ such that $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ integrates to zero. One may have continuity equations for $\exp(ipx)s$ at $x=0$ and the first derivative, namely $A+B=C$ and $Ap_1 - p_1B = p_2C$, but at the same time, one the LHS and RHS of $x=0$, one may have $A\exp(ip_1x) + B\exp(-ip_1x)$ and $C\exp(ip_2x)$ and multiplying these by their complex conjugates and integrating over x should yield $AA+BB$ on the LHS and CC on the RHS. These are the quantity/probability values which do not require a clock. The continuity equation $A+B=C$ on the other hand leads to $AA + BB + 2AB = CC$, which is fine because $A+B=C$ only holds at $x=0$, but there is physical meaning of the terms $A\exp(ip_1x) + B\exp(-ip_1x)$ and

$C_{exp}(ip2x)$ which represent non-clock based quantity/probability measurements which give rise to the scheme which uses A,B,C in the first place.